

ISic3705

I.Sicily inscription 3705

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

plaster

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat, wall of tomb in hypogeum 17, St Agatha catacombs, Rabat

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, Malta, Catacomb of S. Agatha

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178090

1. τόπος Διονυσίας □

2. ἡ κὲ Εἰρήνας □

3. ²menorah²

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 178090

Bibliography

Noy, D. 1993. Jewish inscriptions of Western Europe. Cambridge. At no.166

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